

Bar Code Scanning Using OpenCV and PyZbar

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Abstract— Using OpenCV and PyZbar, this session exposes attendees to the realm of Bar code scanning. Participants will investigate how real-time Bar code scanning applications can be used in practise. The course introduces the fundamentals of video capture with OpenCV and shows how to recognise and decode Bar codes with PyZbar. Also covered are methods for improving the user interface by superimposing visual cues over discovered Bar codes. Participants will learn how to combine scanning codes with databases so that actions based on decoded data are possible. The use of session variables to hold user information is highlighted in the webinar.

Keywords- OpenCV; Image Processing; Machine learning; PyZbar. Computer vision

I. INTRODUCTION

In different areas, barcode scanners are now an essential tool in wide range. They helps to to read information from barcodes, streamlining processes and enhancing data management in a proper and efficient way . In recent years, the use of computer vision and machine learning have significantly increased the development of barcode scanning technology. Using the PyZbar library and OpenCV, this seminar paper explores the use of barcode scanning. Task automation is vital and relies heavily on barcode scanning. Developers may create strong and dependable barcode scanning systems that can extract data from a variety of barcode types, including QR codes and conventional barcodes, by utilising the capabilities of PyZbar and OpenCV. From retail and logistics to healthcare and transportation, barcode scanners are now an essential tool in a wide range of fields. They offer a practical and effective method to read information from barcodes, streamlining processes and enhancing data management. The developments in computer vision and machine learning have significantly speed up the development of barcode scanning technology in recent years.

Using the PyZbar library and OpenCV, this seminar paper explores the use of barcode scanning. Task automation is vital and relies heavily on barcode scanning. Developers may create strong and dependable barcode scanning systems that

can extract data from a variety of barcode types by utilising the capabilities of PyZbar and OpenCV.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The barcode scanner utilizes computer vision techniques provided by OpenCV to detect and extract barcode information from images or video streams. PyZBar is then employed to decode the extracted barcode data and provide the corresponding information, such as product details or unique identifiers. Different studies was conducted in this computer vision

Salah Elaskariab in his paper titled “Barcode to Track Student Attendance and Assets in Higher Education Institutions “[1] says in terms of asset tracking, the most frequent problems are human errors in data collection, inaccurate inventory estimates, and processing time waste. These problems can be addressed with the aid of automated identification and data capture systems. In order to read and analyse student attendance data in classroom settings and to keep track of a periodic inventory of the assets housed within the college facilities, such as devices, equipment, office furniture, classrooms, and laboratories, this article investigates the installation of one such system, barcode technology.

Shah Faisal Darwaisha in his paper titled “Biometric identification on android smartphones” [2] says a suggestion made for the African Cashew Initiative's biometric farmer identification system. The goal of the African Cashew Initiative is to organise and assist cashew producers in five African project countries. The research demonstrates the use of biometric identification in sizable datasets and offers findings about the effectiveness and precision of the suggested approach. This work is a first attempt at offline biometric identification on smartphones and offers early findings for wide-scale implementation.

Erik Johansson in his paper titled ” Fast visual recognition of Scots pine boards using template matching”[3] says Rescanning 44 of the boards and comparing the results to the broader dataset allowed for the evaluation of the board

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recognition method. While lowering the pixel densities of the board images (down sampling the images), three different template matching methods have been examined. Additionally, the impact of different board lengths has been examined, and a measurement of the computational speed of recognition in relation to database size has been made. The open-source software programme OpenCV was used for the tests because of its highly optimised code, which is necessary for applications with high production speeds.

Dwi Sunaryono in his paper titled "An android based course attendance system using face recognition"[4] says on mobile devices with near field communication, biometric recognition, barcodes, and QR codes. However, the earlier systems had slow processing times and had poor accuracy. This study intends to suggest an Android-based face-recognition course attendance system. A QR code with the course details was created and posted at the front of the classroom to ensure that the student would show up for the class. The student merely needed to use his or her smartphone to take a photo of their face and a QR code that was shown. After then, the server received the image to process the attendance.

Tsukasa Kudo in his paper titled "A Proposal for Article Management Method Using Wearable Camera" [5] says he emphasises that a worker's entering and departing activities affect the inventory. In addition, he suggests using deep learning to automatically gather a target inventory from videos of personnel at work. The workers' wearable cameras are used to record the videos. Different deep learning models are trained for various scenarios in order to increase distinction accuracy. Additionally, multiple consecutive images of one target are extracted from the video and used.

Hongwei Li in his paper titled "Smartphone application-based measurements of stem-base width and plant height in rice seedling"[6] says the purpose of carrying out these tiresome and repetitive measurement activities, we create a smartphone application. The reference item and rice seedling were included in an image using the built smartphone application, and the foreground and background were separated using image pre-processing. By comparing the heights of the foreground contours, it was possible to distinguish between the picture of the reference object and the image of the rice seedling in the foreground. The rice seedling image was used to measure the actual stem-base width and plant height by using the scale factor that was determined from the reference object image. In order to determine the measurement accuracy, the outcomes of automatic measurements under various settings were compared to those of manual measurements.

Stack overflow [7] says how to detect the QR code using the original png image

III. MOTIVATION

For simple login systems, barcode scanning with OpenCV and PyZBar can be used. By combining these technologies, users can scan a barcode that is linked to their login information, doing away with the need for manual username and password submission. Barcode pictures can be captured and processed using OpenCV's image processing tools, and PyZBar decodes the barcode data. In addition to streamlining the login process, this strategy improves security by lowering the possibility of user error when entering passwords. Additionally, it offers a seamless user experience because users may access their accounts or systems by just scanning a barcode with the cameras on their smartphones. Barcode scanning with OpenCV and PyZBar offers a solution for login authentication, whether it is for mobile applications, access control systems, or secure online platforms.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for scanning barcodes using OpenCV and PyZbar involves the following steps:

- A. Capturing of Image:** The id card Image is captured using a high resolution Camera. For performing the remaining steps, the characters in the captured image should be in a readable form. Using a better camera with more definition and resolution will increase the success ratio of the system.
- B. Pre-process:** In pre-processing, the cost of computing the image information is minimised. The images will either be in a format compatible with multimedia standards or in raw form. These graphics will often be in RGB mode, which has three channels: red, green, and blue. The number of channels determines how much colour information is included in the image. The image has to be transformed to grayscale.
- C. Localize:** In essence, localization is the process of binarizing an image. The image is then made black and white. As earlier studies have shown, we employ localization to highlight characters and suppress background.
- D. Detection:** The barcode in image will be detected by symbol location algorithm using of pattern recognition techniques, such as edge detection and contour analysis, to identify the characteristic patterns of barcodes and QR codes.
- E. Decoding:** After detecting the barcode, several decoding algorithms were used, like Code39, Code128, EAN, PDF417 etc by checking in lookup table.
- F. Error Correction:** It enables bar codes in particular to be deciphered even if parts of the code have been broken or

hidden, are frequently used in bar codes. Since PyZbar has algorithms for handling error correction, it can reliably read even damaged or deteriorated bar codes.

G. Authenticating: The value that is extracted by decode function after error correction will be checked with the database and corresponding user will be selected

Overall, the methodology for barcode reader is done by getting the image from user camera and barcode data will be taken by using decode function in PyZbar library.

V. BUILD MODEL

By the following steps the user can directly login to system by reading the corresponding bar code.

Importing Libraries

```
from django.views.decorators import gzip
from pyzbar.pyzbar import decode
import cv2
```

- A. CV2:** The OpenCV, also referred to as the Open Source Computer Vision Library, or simply the CV2 package, is a widely-utilized computer vision library renowned for its diverse image and video processing applications. The application presents a diverse array of features and tools that facilitate the manipulation and analysis of photographs, detection and surveillance of mobile entities, the implementation of filters and variations, as well as other functionalities.
- B. PyZbar :** An essential component for decoding barcodes and QR codes in Python is the decode function found in the PyZbar module. A Python package called PyZbar offers access to the ZBar barcode scanning library.
- C. gzip:** The Django web framework encompasses an attribute referred to as the @gzip.gzip_page decorator, which enables the implementation of the gzip approach for condensing HTTP responses. To expedite data transmission and optimize network efficiency, diminution of response data delivered from the server to the client is employed.

Integrating the camera in webpage

```
@csrf_exempt
@gzip.gzip_page
def video_feed_view(request):

    return StreamingHttpResponse(log_bar(request),
                                content_type='multipart/x-mixed-replace; boundary=frame')
```

Capturing of image and detecting the barcode

```
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
while True:
    ret, frame = cap.read()
    barcodes = decode(frame)
```

Connecting the database and session with barcode data

```
for barcode in barcodes:
    (x, y, w, h) = barcode.rect
    cv2.rectangle(frame, (x, y), (x + w, y + h), (0, 0, 255), 2)
    barcode_text = barcode.data.decode("utf-8")
    cv2.putText(frame, barcode_text, (x, y - 10), cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, 0.5, (0, 0, 255), 2)
    if tbl_login.objects.filter(uid=barcode_text).exists():
        user=tbl_login.objects.get(uid=barcode_text)

        email=user.email
        password=user.password
        request.session['email'] = email

        request.session.save()
        subject = "AMICE Canteen "
        from_email = settings.EMAIL_HOST_USER
        recipient_list = [email]
        htmlgen = "Forgot credentials ?"+"  
Username:"+email+"\n"+"password :"+password+"
        send_mail(subject, htmlgen, from_email, recipient_list)
```

VI. RESULT

Performance prediction

The System took more than ten seconds for recognizing the id card and extracting the number. One of the key factor that determined performance was the size of input image and its clarity.

Using opencv

Fig: 1

Fig:1 shows how the user's camera was accessed and it leads to detect the barcode using the python package OpenCV

Unregistered person

Fig: 2

Fig:2 shows the detection and decode of barcode of a unregistered person. It is done by the decode function inside the python package PyZbar . It shows authentication failed message because the user with admission number 13253 was not registered in the database

Registered person

Fig: 3

Fig:3 shows the detection and decode of barcode of a unregistered person using the python package PyZbar . It shows authentication success message because the user with admission number 13294 was registered in the database

VII. CONCLUSION

Using PyZbar and OpenCV, this seminar paper investigates the subject of barcode readers. A complete solution for barcode scanning and decoding has been made possible by the integration of these two potent libraries. Using PyZbar and OpenCV together gave users a dependable and effective barcode scanning solution with a wide range of potential applications. Overall, the usefulness and adaptability of PyZbar and OpenCV for barcode reading have been proven in this seminar work. A solid foundation for creating barcode scanning systems with precise and effective decoding capabilities is provided by the integration of these libraries. Through process simplification and efficiency boosts, barcode readers based on PyZbar and OpenCV have the potential to revolutionise a number of sectors.

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